

1 **Tbx21 (T-bet) expression is silenced in the hematopoietic system in humans with asthma.**

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6 Deletion of T-bet in mice results in development of asthma, a Th2 disease caused by loss of a Th1 lineage
7 commitment gene. We studied total transcription by RNA-sequencing in the blood of humans with asthma
8 to define the essential components of the asthma gene signature in the human hematopoietic
9 compartment and for identification of novel therapeutic targets. Surprisingly, among the genes whose
10 expression was most significantly silenced across the entire human transcriptome in the blood in humans
11 with asthma was Tbx21, the gene encoding human T-bet. The data demonstrate that silencing expression
12 of a homeobox factor that guides HSC differentiation in the immune system to specific cell subsets results
13 in disease by skewing lineage commitment, with the pathology a direct function of homeobox silencing and
14 whose contribution has previously been demonstrated in a genetically engineered animal model.

15 **References**

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